

Full Bayesian sequence, phases, and interval length

1. Full Bayesian sequence plot

2. Bayesian phases

3. Bayesian sequence interval length

Phase	Interval length (years)	Percentage certainty
IV-C	687-1047	95.4%
V-C	0-46	95.4%
V-B	0-44	95.4%
V-C	0-737	95.4%